

DEVELOPING THE SKILLS OF PERFORMING ON MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL GRADES

**Rakhmatov Bekzod Juroevich, Teacher of the
Accordion Class at the Children's Music and
Art School No. 8, Sherabad District, Surkhandarya Region.**

Abstract

This article analyzes the methods and techniques used in teaching the performance of the accordion in primary music classes. It explores the role of teaching accordion performance in developing children's musical skills, creativity, and interest in music. Various pedagogical methods, such as demonstration, practical exercises, visual and audiovisual materials, interactive pedagogical games, rhythm and dynamics training, and collaborative work in orchestra, are discussed as effective ways to shape children's musical abilities and enhance their creative activities. The article emphasizes the importance of using these diverse teaching methods to engage students and stimulate their creative skills, contributing to the development of their artistic expression and interest in music.

Keywords

primary education, accordion performance, pedagogical methods, rhythm, dynamics, practical exercises, visual materials, audiovisual materials, interactive games, collaborative work, orchestra performance, online platforms, children's creative development, aesthetic music education, psychology, motivation.

1. Introduction

In primary education, musical performance, particularly playing instruments, plays a significant role in the aesthetic and moral development of young children. Music education, especially through instrumental performance, helps children develop essential skills such as breathing, communication, emotional expression, coordination, and attention. Therefore,

teaching musical instrument performance in primary school grades is a crucial pedagogical process for children's development.

Research aim and objectives: The aim of this article is to analyze the methods and approaches used in teaching musical instrument performance in primary school grades. The article explores the main directions of instrumental teaching and evaluates their pedagogical effectiveness.

2. The Importance of Instrumental Performance in Children's Education

Instrumental performance teaches young children several important skills, such as understanding rhythm, melody, and dynamics, as well as reading musical notes and performing correctly. Additionally, instrumental performance fosters children's creativity, enhances their emotional world, and deepens their interest in music.

Musical education is vital for the intellectual, physical, and moral development of children. Playing an instrument helps improve motor coordination and cognitive activity while cultivating emotional and aesthetic sensitivity.

3. Methods of Teaching Musical Instrument Performance in Primary School Grades

1. Demonstration Method

In the demonstration method, the teacher demonstrates how to play the instrument, and students observe and learn from these demonstrations. This method is effective in helping young children understand rhythm, musical dynamics, and learn how to read notes correctly. The teacher's example assists students in performing the notes correctly and accurately.

2. Practical Exercises (Hands-On Learning)

The practical method is the primary approach for teaching instrumental performance. In this method, students develop their skills by repeating exercises, melodies, and technical techniques. In each exercise, the teacher provides additional guidance and corrections. The teacher's feedback helps students overcome technical mistakes.

3. Use of Visual and Audiovisual Materials

Using visual aids (such as note diagrams, charts, and images) or audiovisual materials (such as videos, interactive programs) enhances the learning process. These materials help children understand the changes in notes, dynamics, and rhythm more effectively. They also attract students' attention and make learning more engaging.

4. Interactive and Collaborative Methods

Interactive teaching methods, such as musical games and communication, help children learn how to perform on instruments. In this approach, children are introduced to musical notes and performance in a more interactive way. Teachers encourage collaborative exercises and communication among students.

5. Learning Rhythm and Dynamics

Instrumental performance requires a strong sense of rhythm and dynamics. In this method, children practice rhythm through games and exercises, improving their ability to interpret and synchronize their movements with the musical elements. They also learn to interpret dynamic changes, such as playing in different tempos or adjusting to softer or louder volumes.

6. Group Work and Ensemble Performance

Teaching children to perform in groups, such as in an orchestra or musical ensemble, is an essential method of instrumental education. Group performance helps students develop collaborative skills, work in harmony, and synchronize their performance with others. Playing together strengthens both individual and collective musical abilities.

7. Using Offline and Online Platforms

Modern technology has proven to be a valuable tool in music education. Mobile apps or online courses provide students with the opportunity to learn notes and perform music interactively. These platforms help enhance children's visual and auditory skills, facilitating a deeper understanding of musical concepts.

4. Conclusion

Teaching instrumental performance in primary school grades plays an important role in the aesthetic, physical, and intellectual development of children. Music education helps children improve their coordination, creativity, and ability to perform correctly. Using various pedagogical methods and techniques in instrumental education contributes to enhancing children's interest in music and developing their creative skills. Every teacher should consider the developmental characteristics of children and choose methods that best suit their needs.

Additionally, modern pedagogical innovations and interactive methods are crucial for teaching musical instruments. These methods help maintain students' attention, enhance their performance skills, and make the learning process more engaging and effective.